

The background of the cover features an aerial photograph of a river winding through a dry, brown landscape. The river is a vibrant blue-green color. In the bottom right corner, there is a dark blue overlay with white, glowing lines and dots, resembling a data visualization or a network map. The text is positioned on the right side of the cover.

International Scientific and Practical Conference

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

PROCEEDINGS
(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

WICAR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

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International Scientific and Practical Conference -2026

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference innovative approaches to water resource management in arid regions in the context of climate change on May 19, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The conference aims to discuss key issues of effective water resource management in arid regions under climate change, develop and apply innovative approaches and mathematical and computational modeling methods, share recent research results and practical experience, and strengthen international academic cooperation in this field.

Key Themes of the Conference:

1. Water Diplomacy and Integrated Approaches in International Relation: Interdisciplinary Approaches to Sustainable Development, Communication and Global Security

- Issues of systemic analysis in international relations and world politics in the context of water diplomacy
- Economic, environmental and energy aspects of sustainable development
- Systemic approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. Mathematical and computer modeling of optimal water resources management under climate change

- Optimal water resource management under climate change
- Modeling water resource dynamics and climate variability
- Methods of applied and computational mathematics in irrigation system modeling.

3. Environmental and Hydrogeological Processes in the Aral Sea Region: Analysis Based on Modern Technologies

- Analysis of hydrogeological processes in the Aral Sea region
- Application of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data technologies to environmental challenges
- Simulation and stochastic modeling of environmental and hydrogeological processes in the Aral region.

The event was conducted in a hybrid format with participation in English, Russian, and Uzbek. The conference provided a high-level platform for scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

The influence of porous layer parameters on hydrodynamic characteristics in laminar flow

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Abstract

This paper presents the interaction of a laminar boundary layer with an adjacent porous substrate, focusing on the mechanisms of friction modulation at the interface. We analyze the influence of key structural parameters, including porosity and layer thickness, on the velocity profile and the drag coefficient due to the porous layer. The process is modeled using the Navier-Stokes equation, taking the porous layer into account, i.e., a single-domain approach is used. The results show that optimized porous coatings can significantly reduce wall shear stress, offering a promising approach for passive flow control in aerodynamic applications.

Keywords: Impact of Porous Layer Parameters on Wall Shear Stress in Laminar Boundary Layer Flows

Introduction

In many environmental and technical processes, porous media play a central role in the control of laminar flow. In hydrodynamic processes, fluid flows interact with heterogeneous porous media. A heterogeneous medium is a combined region containing a free zone and a porous layer. Examples include fluid flow in canals and rivers in the presence of sediments, flow with vegetation, flow with an uneven bottom, flow through a silt layer containing a porous medium, etc. The study of the laws of continuous media flow through a heterogeneous layer is one of the areas of research in the field of multiphase media mechanics [1]. Прикладные задачи возникают в различных исследованиях геологических систем, относящихся к добыче полезных ископаемых, их очистке и переработке [2, 3]. Здесь имеет место трудности в создания математических моделей из-за сложности явлений [4]. С одной стороны, течение в свободной зоне описываются уравнениями Навье-Стокса, в пористой среды используется осреднённые уравнения [5].

There are two main classical approaches to describing such problems [6, 7]. The first approach models the medium using a single equation, and performs calculations using end-to-end computations. The second approach uses a separate equation for each medium, and performs calculations separately for each subdomain, with different interphase boundary conditions applied to the interboundary zone. This paper considers a model based on generalized Navier-Stokes equations. These equations are obtained by averaging over a characteristic volume of the porous medium and are written for the entire computational domain. For the numerical implementation of this model, a calculation algorithm based on the control volume method has been developed [8].

In [9-11], an interpenetrating model was used to study flows with porous media. The authors of [12-13] successfully applied the control volume method to numerically solve the Navier-Stokes equation, taking into account the rotation of a cylinder in a viscous flow. Work [14] is devoted to modeling flows with porous media using the viscous shallow water equation. Works [15-16] are devoted to modeling water processes for open flow (Saint-Venant equations) and numerical implementation.

Mathematical model and numerical method

Let us consider the Navier-Stokes equation with an additional term, describing the flow of a porous layer [6-7]. Then the flow of the liquid phase is described by a system of equations (two-dimensional case):

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) - Cu, \quad (1)$$

$$u \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial x} + \vartheta \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \vartheta}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \vartheta}{\partial y^2} \right) - C\vartheta, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Here, u, ϑ are the longitudinal and transverse flow velocities, p is the pressure, ν is the climatic viscosity, and C is the interaction coefficient associated with the Darcy forces. The following equations are found in the literature: $C = f\mu/k$, f is the porosity of the medium, μ is the dynamic viscosity, and k is the permeability of the porous medium (determines the ability of a fluid to penetrate into a porous material. High permeability usually increases friction by entraining the flow inside) associated with the Kozeny-Karman formula, and is associated with

$$k = \frac{d^2 f^3}{150(1-f)^2}$$

Let us reduce equations (1)-(3) to dimensionless form.

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{Re} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) - Ku, \quad (4)$$

$$u \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial x} + \vartheta \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial y} = -\frac{1}{Re} \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \vartheta}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \vartheta}{\partial y^2} \right) - K\vartheta, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Here $Re = hU\rho_0/\mu$ is the Reynolds number; U is the characteristic velocity; h is the characteristic size, the dimensionless coefficient K has the following value: is the Reynolds number; U is the characteristic velocity; h is the characteristic size, the dimensionless coefficient K has the following value:

$$K = \left(\frac{h}{d} \right)^2 \frac{150(1-f)}{f^3 \cdot Re}$$

Dimensionless variables are related to dimensional variables as follows (here variables with primes are dimensional):

$$x = \frac{x'}{h}, y = \frac{y'}{h}, u = \frac{u'}{U}, v = \frac{v'}{U}, p = \frac{Re p'}{\rho_0 U^2}$$

Equations (4)-(6) allow us to study the flow of fluid both from inside and outside a porous medium, since at $f = 1$ we obtain the Navier-Stokes equations for an incompressible fluid, at $f \neq 1$ the Navier-Stokes filtration equations, and these equations are suitable for the entire region under consideration.

The flow region is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Flow region

The channel height is h , the lower part of which, with a height of δ , is filled with a porous medium. Our goal is to determine the influence of flow parameters and the porous layer on the flow hydrodynamics and the influence on the drag coefficient at the interface.

For the purpose of numerically solving the system of differential equations (4)–(6), the control volume method was chosen [8].

Discretization of the equations was performed by integration over control volumes, followed by approximation of the flows through the cell faces. To relate velocity and pressure, the SIMPLE algorithm [8] was used, generalized to the system of equations (4)–(6), including terms responsible for the influence of the porous medium. At each iteration, discrete equations were solved for the velocity components (and other unknowns, if present in (4)–(6)), after which the pressure and velocity were corrected from the pressure correction equation, ensuring that the continuity equation was satisfied. Convergence was monitored by the residuals of the equations and by the stabilization of integral characteristics (e.g., flow rate and pressure drop/drag coefficient).

It should be noted that equations of type (4)–(6) are widely used to describe flows in the presence of porous inclusions and porous layers; similar formulations were used to study the flow structure in [5]. This allows us to compare the obtained results with known approaches and, if necessary, verify them against published data.

Boundary conditions were specified as follows. A no-slip condition (zero velocity at the wall) was used on the solid walls of the computational domain. At the channel inlet, a hydrostatic pressure distribution and a velocity profile corresponding to Poiseuille flow were specified, ensuring correct initialization of the inlet flow and reducing the influence of the inlet region on the studied region. At the outlet, a "soft" boundary condition was applied, minimizing the artificial influence of the boundary on the flow (e.g., zero longitudinal gradients for velocities and/or a fixed reference pressure).

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = 0, v = 0.$$

Results and discussions

To analyze the obtained solutions to the problem, let us consider the friction coefficient [17]:

$$C_f = \frac{\tau_w}{0.5\rho U^2}, \quad (7)$$

where τ_w is the frictional stress at the interface.

Using the nondimensionalization parameters, the expression for the frictional stress can be written as follows:

$$\tau_w = \frac{\mu U}{h} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial n} \right), \quad (8)$$

where n is the dimensionless outward normal to the bottom surface, and the index "w" denotes the bottom surface.

Substituting expression (7) into equation (6), we obtain an expression for the friction coefficient:

$$C_f = \frac{2}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)_w \quad (9)$$

Fig. 2 shows the numerical results of the drag coefficient calculated using formula (9).

Fig. 2. Change in the resistance coefficient at the interface with different porosity.
 $Re=100$, $\delta=0.2$

Figure 2 shows the drag coefficient for a channel with a porous layer at various porosity values. Lines with asterisks correspond to porosity ($f = 0.000001$), triangles to porosity ($f = 0.9$), and rectangles to porosity ($f = 0.99$). These values allow us to trace the transition from a nearly impermeable structure (very low porosity) to significantly more permeable porous media.

An analysis of Figure 2 shows that the ratio of the characteristic channel length (in this case, its width) to the characteristic grain size of the porous layer significantly influences the drag coefficient. For a fixed channel width, a decrease in the characteristic grain size results in drag coefficient values for the porous layer becoming closer to those typical of a smooth solid wall. Physically, this means that with a sufficiently fine structure of the porous material, the influence of microgeometry averages out, and the flow near the boundary behaves similarly to flow near a solid wall.

It should be emphasized that a porous layer with very low porosity can serve as an approximate model of a solid wall, since filtration transport through such a layer is negligible. Therefore, the curve marked with asterisks ($f = 0.000001$) can, with a sufficient degree of accuracy, be considered a reference case corresponding to a solid wall (or the limiting transition to one). This is convenient for comparison: the deviation of the other curves from this dependence characterizes the degree of influence of the permeability and structure of the porous medium on hydraulic losses.

The graphs in Figure 2 also demonstrate a general trend: the presence of a porous layer, as well as an increase in its porosity, lead to a decrease in the drag coefficient. In other words, when moving from a less porous to a more porous structure, hydraulic losses decrease. This effect can be interpreted as a consequence of increasing layer permeability: part of the flow or momentum is redistributed near the boundary, which leads to a decrease in drag compared to the case of an impermeable wall.

In addition to the influence of porosity and characteristic grain size, calculations were performed to assess the role of the porous layer thickness. Thickness determines how deeply the effects of filtration and flow interaction with the porous structure manifest themselves, and therefore can significantly change the total pressure losses. Figure 3 shows the drag coefficient for a dimensionless porous layer thickness of (0.1). A comparison of the results in Figure 3 with the data in Fig. 2 allows us to separate the influence of the geometric parameters of the porous layer (thickness, grain size) from the influence of its structural parameter - porosity - and thereby clarify the contribution of each factor to the formation of flow resistance

Fig. 3 Change in the resistance coefficient at the interphase boundary at different porosity.
 $Re=100$, $\delta=0.1$

A comparative analysis of Figures 2 and 3 demonstrates agreement with the statement presented in Figure 2. Based on a comparison of these figures, it can be concluded that decreasing the thickness of the porous layer leads to a decrease in bottomhole resistance, all other conditions being equal. This conclusion also holds true with increasing Reynolds number (Figure 4).

Fig.4 Change in the resistance coefficient at the interphase boundary at different porosity.
 $Re=500$, $h/d=100$

Conclusion

Boundary porous structures have the property of reducing drag, with the higher the porosity of the layer, the lower the drag.

Decreasing the thickness of the porous layer helps reduce drag, which helps control flow in channels.

Using an equation within a single computational domain is preferable to the separate-zone method. This eliminates the uncertainty of the empirical Beavers-Joseph coefficient and allows for a physically correct description of momentum diffusion into the porous layer.

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